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Sri Endang Kornita
University of Riau
Jl. Binawidya Km 12.5, 28291,
Pekanbaru Riau, Indonesia
Faculty of Economics and Business

Ulfira Isbah
University of Riau
Jl. Binawidya Km 12.5, 28291,
Pekanbaru Riau, Indonesia
Faculty of Economics and Business

Separen Separen
University of Riau
Jl. Binawidya Km 12.5, 28291,
Pekanbaru Riau, Indonesia
Faculty of Economics and Business

Bunga Chintia Utami
University of Riau
Jl. Binawidya Km 12.5, 28291,
Pekanbaru Riau, Indonesia
Faculty of Economics and Business

DIFFUSION OF SEXUAL VIOLENCE PREVENTION AND HANDLING POLICY INNOVATIONS (PPKS) IN THE RIAU

Abstract: One area of concern in realizing gender forms is something that attracts gender attention. The purpose of this study is to analyze the diffusion process of policy innovations of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Violence (PPKS) in the academic community at the University of Riau. The data used is primary data using 100 respondents from the academic community. The analytical method used is descriptive quantitative by spreading the research through google form. The results showed that most of the samples showed the results were at the implementation stage. This shows that the majority of the Riau University academic community have known, made decisions to accept policies and implement policies in daily life related to the Minister of Education and Culture Policy Number 30 of 2021 concerning Sexual Prevention and Treatment (PPKS) in Higher Education.

Key words: Gender, PPKS, Diffusion, Innovation, Implementation, Permendikbudristek.

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Introduction

Gender is an important element in development, this is because all aspects related to development or

sub-development will involve and come into direct contact with humans, meaning that humans or society are the main essence of development in a broad sense.

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The development paradigm in any angle needs to see the relationship between the needs and interests of the community as the main factor of development [1].

The world's high attention and appreciation for the achievement of gender justice and equality as part of the success of development goals, requires every country to play a role in achieving development targets in all lines of development[2], [3], including Indonesia. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) in 1948 is one of the international human rights instruments in the realization of promoting and encouraging human rights and freedom as the foundation of justice, freedom and peace [4].

The agenda for the Sustainable Development Goals (TPB/SDGs) was formulated at the global level by involving the leaders of 193 UN member countries at the end of September 2015 raising the issue of gender in the fifth goal, namely achieving gender equality[5]. Gender mainstreaming is part of the development strategy in achieving gender equality and justice[6]–[8]. Gender equality and social inclusion (GESI) requires the implementation of equitable development in all lines of society including gender, women and children. Therefore, development policies that are in favor of gender equality are needed.

One area of concern in realizing gender equality is gender inequality in the form of sexual violence. After the collapse of the New Order regime in 1998 and the entry of the reformation era, many conflict events occurred in Indonesia and women have always been the target of various forms of violence, including sexual violence. Violence, discrimination and sexual violence against women is one of the violations of human rights in Indonesia. Based on data compiled by The National Commission on Violence Against Women of the Republic of Indonesia—commonly referred to as Komnas Perempuan—throughout 2020 there were 2,389 cases of violence and 53% of them were sexual violence.

The complexity of social problems regarding development can be sourced from injustice, including gender inequality, then if it is explored more deeply, it is the women who are often the most disadvantaged. For example, women's participation in access, many women do not have the same access as men both in decision making or opportunities to education, especially for women in rural areas who are vulnerable to dropping out of school[9]. The basic reason is the view of rural communities who still see that women cannot be separated from their duties and functions in the domestic area, in practice their role as mothers and taking care of the family is narrowed, so that it is considered that there is no need for higher education and developing their potential outside of domestic work.

According to the media *Kumparan News* published on November 12, 2021, there are 53% of violence against women that occurs not only in

personal spaces, but also in public spaces such as educational institutions. More than 67 cases of sexual violence that occurred in the educational environment. Violence occurs from students to students, lecturers to lecturers, or other employees and workers. The head of Komnas Perempuan, Andy Yentritani, revealed that many cases of sexual violence were not reported to legal channels because they were considered consensual behavior.

Based on the results of a survey conducted by the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia in 2019, it was revealed that there were 1,011 cases of sexual violence on campus. Meanwhile, the results of a survey conducted by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia revealed that 70% of students, the academic community, educators, and employees stated that cases of violence did occur on campus.

In the era of globalization with the advancement of sophisticated technology, many women do not know and are not aware that they have been sexually harassed. This happens because of ignorance of the definition of sexual harassment. Things that always happen and are experienced by women when complaining and reporting sexual harassment problems are always being pressured or intimidated so that the perpetrators do not dare to speak up, even superiors always ask for evidence of the abuse experienced by the victim[10], [11]. In fact, it is very difficult to prove because it is nearly impossible for the victim to have recorded a video when she was harassed by the perpetrator. This is why many abusers are left untouched by the law and never brought to justice.

So far, there is no legal umbrella for sexual violence and harassment in the Higher Education environment so that perpetrators of sexual harassment are free to roam and victims of harassment so far have not dared to report and have not received legal protection. Slowly but surely, one by one the problems of sexual harassment that occurred on campus were exposed in the public media, cases of sexual harassment involving well-known universities in Indonesia.

In response to this condition, the Minister of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology (Mendikbudristek) Nadiem Makarim made a policy by issuing Permendikbud Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in Higher Education as one of the policy steps to address gender inequality in education. forms of sexual violence. This regulation is very important to be implemented immediately, because the problems of sexual harassment that have been detected so far are only a few of the many problems of sexual violence in universities that have not been revealed, so cases of violence in universities that have occurred so far are like pile of icebergs.

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Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in Higher Education is the latest idea issued by the Minister of Education and Culture [12]. This Permendikbud is a regulation or legal umbrella for the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in Higher Education which must be known, understood and implemented by the entire academic community in Higher Education.

Development basically aims to improve people's lives, both men and women as subjects of development, including the point in it is to achieve gender justice. In order for the development program as outlined in the policy to achieve its goals and objectives, development communication is required in delivering the program. One of development communication is in the form of innovation diffusion in development. Diffusion of innovation is a form of communication to convey development programs to the target community so that the objectives of the program can be achieved properly.

For the implementation of government programs through Permendikbud Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in Higher Education to realize gender equality and eliminate sexual violence, an appropriate delivery process is needed to the program target community. Therefore, the study of the diffusion of innovations on these government programs. Based on the above and the limited study of the diffusion of innovations in gender development, especially those related to sexual violence, it is necessary to study the diffusion of innovations against the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 30 of 2021. Then in addition to facing the complexity of the existing issues, gender studies to date still have its own charm to continue to be studied as a response to existing social phenomena. Therefore, efforts are needed to find solutions through various sciences, especially in social science disciplines. This study aims to analyze the process of diffusion of policy innovations from the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in the academic community at the University of Riau.

Literature Review

The concept of gender was born as a result of sociological and cultural processes related to the division of roles and positions between men and women in a society [13]. This shows that in the process of community development, habits, social and cultural values have been formed that distinguish a person's role based on gender [14], [15]. The social roles of women are usually considered second class and different from that of men [16], [17]. Concern about class differences will lead to easy oppression, violence and inequality.

The term gender focuses on the differences in the character of men and women based on socio-cultural constructions related to their nature, status, position, and role in society. Mosse in [18] explained that during the 1970s-1980s there were three approaches to women's studies, namely WiD (Women in Development), WaD (Women and Development), and GaD (Gender and Development). Each approach has different characteristics. The differences between the three can be seen as follows:

1. The WiD approach is strongly influenced by modernization theory thinking, which considers that women's backwardness is caused more by individual factors such as low education. This approach explains that the involvement of women in development activities is the main focus of overcoming inequality.
2. The WaD approach is influenced by the neo marxist feminist approach. The main focus of this approach looks at the relationship of women in the development process. The development process often leads to the marginalization of women. This is due to the existence of an unfair social, economic and political structure in society. The underdevelopment of women is considered to be the result of this unfair structure. The WaD approach sees that one form of impoverishment of one particular gender, in this case women, is caused by gender. There are several processes of marginalization of women due to gender differences that arise from various sources such as government policies, beliefs, religious interpretations, traditional beliefs and habits or scientific assumptions.
3. The GaD approach emerged in the 1980s, known as an effort to empower women. This approach is strongly influenced by the socialist feminist approach. GaD sees women as agents of change rather than passive objects in development. This approach criticizes the relationship between women's participation in the economy does not always raise the status of women. The low level of participation is correlated with the low status of women but the involvement of women is actually considered to plunge women, because they will be made into virtual slaves. The GaD approach emphasizes the need for empowerment in women and changing social constructions which are only objects in the development process. This approach understands development goals for women in terms of independence and internal strength and places more emphasis on making laws that address equality between men and women.

The theory of diffusion of innovations popularized by Everett Rogers in 1964. In his book entitled "Diffusion of Innovations" explains diffusion is a process when an innovation is communicated through several channels with a certain period of time

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in a social system. Rogers explained that there are 5 stages in the diffusion of innovations, namely knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation and confirmation. The five stages of innovation adoption are [19]:

1. The knowledge stage. In this stage, a person does not yet have information about the new innovation. For that information about the innovation must be conveyed through various communication channels. So that people know the existence of this innovation.
2. The persuasion stage. In the second stage, more of the process of measuring the benefits that will be obtained from adopting the innovation personally. Based on evaluation and discussion with others, a person will begin to tend to adopt or reject the innovation. At this stage there is a process of convincing the public that the innovation has many advantages over the
3. The decision stage. In this stage, a person makes the final decision whether to adopt or reject the innovation. However, after this decision has been taken, changes can still be made if deemed necessary.
4. Implementation stage. In this stage, a person begins to carry out innovations by continuing to learn about the innovation.
5. The confirmation stage. This stage is in the form of seeking other people's opinions from various sources whether the decision is correct or whether it is necessary to abandon the innovation.

Figure 1. Rogers' Innovation Diffusion Process Model.

Society in responding to innovation can be grouped into 5 groups. According to Rogers and Shoemaker [20], people who face a diffusion of innovation absorption (innovation diffusion) are grouped into the following groups [21]:

1. Innovators are people who basically like new things, and are diligent in conducting experiments.
2. Early adopters, namely people who are influential, where friends around them get information, and are people who are more advanced than those around them.
3. Early majority, namely people who accept innovation one step ahead of the average of most other people.
4. Late majority, namely people who are only willing to accept an innovation if according to their assessment everyone around them has accepted the innovation.

5. Laggards, which is the last layer in accepting an innovation.

This theory will be able to explain the diffusion of innovation in the Riau University Academic Community which has entered the adoption stage and how the Riau University community group responds to policy innovations for the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS). Identification of problems using the diffusion of innovation theory will facilitate decision/policy makers regarding appropriate policy recommendations in accordance with existing conditions in the field.

According to [22], in the Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence, it shows that the Minister of Education, Culture, Research and Technology Regulation number 30 of 2021 is seen as a progressive step in the midst of anxiety over the high level of sexual violence in universities, then the formulation of rules and prevention mechanisms More technically,

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sexual violence as a derivative rule from Permendikbudristek in higher education must involve all actors from the academic community.

Data And Methodology

This study uses primary data, with a population of 36,960 people consisting of 1,452 lecturers (3.93%), 428 educators (1.15%) and 35,080 students (94.91%). The sample in this study was 100 people who were determined by the Slovin formula, then the stratification method determined the number of samples from each academic community at the University of Riau based on their respective proportions. The analytical technique used to analyze the study of the diffusion of innovation policies on prevention and handling of sexual violence (PPKS) at the Riau University academic community uses quantitative descriptive analysis method by distributing research questionnaires via google form

to the Riau University academic community as the research sample.

Results

The research on the diffusion of innovation policies on prevention and handling of sexual violence (PPKS) in the Riau University academic community according to that contained in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 uses the theory of diffusion of innovations from Everett Rogers, where there are 5 stages in the diffusion of innovations, namely knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation and confirmation. The results of the research based on each stage in the diffusion of innovations in the prevention and handling of sexual violence (PPKS) policies in the Riau University academic community as outlined in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in Higher Education are described in table 1 below:

Table 1. Research Results of the Stages of Diffusion of Innovations from the Riau University Academic Community on PPKS Policy in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021

No.	Innovation Diffusion Stage	Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Knowledge	-	-
2	Persuasion	-	-
3	Decision making	20	20
4	Implementation	73	73
5	Confirmation	7	7

Source: Researchers' Data (2022)

From the results of the study, it is known that there is no academic community at the University of Riau who is in the early stage, namely the stage of knowledge and persuasion in the diffusion of innovations towards the policy of preventing and handling sexual violence (PPKS) in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021. While in this third stage there are 20 percent of the Riau University community who are already at the decision-making stage of the prevention and handling of sexual violence (PPKS) policies at the University of Riau in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021. The fourth stage in the innovation diffusion policy is the implementation stage which is the most common stage in the Riau University academic community in the policy of preventing and handling sexual violence (PPKS), as many as 73 percent of respondents are at this stage. Then in the last stage, namely the confirmation stage, there are only 7 percent of respondents who are in the confirmation stage in the policy on the prevention and handling of sexual violence (PPKS) at the University of Riau as stated in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021.

Discussion

The following explains the discussion of the results of the research on the diffusion of innovation

policies on prevention and handling of sexual violence (PPKS) in the academic community of the University of Riau based on Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in Higher Education Environments by referring to the stages of diffusion of innovations from Everett Rogers.

Stage of Knowledge

The knowledge stage is the early stage in policy diffusion and innovation. At this stage a person is considered to have no information about new innovations, namely in this case the policy of preventing and handling sexual violence. Therefore, information regarding the PPKS policy needs to be conveyed or disseminated in various communication channels using mass media, social media and electronic media, so that the public becomes aware of the existence of innovations related to PPKS policies, especially in the university environment contained in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in Higher Education.

The results of the study indicate that there is no Riau University academic community, namely lecturers, students, and educators who are at this stage related to Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021

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concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in Higher Education. This means that all the academics of the University of Riau already know the policies for preventing and handling sexual violence (PPKS) which are described in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in Higher Education. This happens because the Riau University academic community is a group of people with higher education levels making it easier for them to access policies related to PPKS that are conveyed through mass media, social media and electronic media, including Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in the College Environment.

Based on these results, it is no longer necessary to disseminate information regarding Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in Higher Education in the Riau University academic community. So that it can be said that the Riau University academic community is the early majority, namely the group of people who accept innovation one step ahead of the average person in accepting PPKS policy innovations related to Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Efforts to Prevent Sexual Violence in the College Environment.

Stage of Persuasion

The persuasion stage is the second stage, after the knowledge stage in the innovation diffusion process. At this stage a person will form an attitude in himself to be able to approve and disapprove of an innovation. In the persuasion stage, someone will find out more information about the innovation, including the advantages or disadvantages of using the information. Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, it shows that there are no respondents or 0% of the Riau University academic community, both lecturers, students, and education staff who are at this stage related to Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in the Higher Education Environment.

Based on the results of the study, it can be seen that respondents, both lecturers, students, and education staff at the University of Riau have agreed to Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 as a legal tool to ensnare perpetrators of sexual violence at the University of Riau and respondents are able to take appropriate and appropriate attitudes if there is a problem of sexual violence in the Riau University environment.

Stage of Decision Making

The decision-making stage is part of the problem-solving process, in the problem-solving process, decision-making includes one of the stages

called the mile stone or referred to as a crucial point and must be passed. The decision-making stages are carried out through a process of analysis, mapping and simulation by taking into account various possible alternatives that are most effective and efficient as well as realistic to be implemented.

Based on the results of the research on the diffusion of innovation policies on Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) at the Academic Community of Riau University, the decision-making stage is the third stage after the knowledge stage and the persuasion stage in the innovation diffusion process and it can be seen that there are 20 respondents or 20% of the community, academics, both lecturers, students, and education personnel who are included in the decision-making category regarding Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in Higher Education.

Stage of Implementation

The majority of the samples showed the results were at the implementation stage. This shows that 73% of the Riau University academic community has known, made a decision to accept policies and implement policies in daily life related to the Minister of Education and Culture Policy Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in Higher Education. One year of implementation of the policy and 73% are already in the implementation stage, it means that the adopter type of the Riau University academic community is in the early adopter type.

Early adopters have the characteristics of those who in the majority together become the early followers of an innovation. Early followers showed a quick response to implementing innovations because it was driven by internal factors that occurred at Riau University after the enactment of Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021. Internal factors could be the characteristics of adopters who are in higher education, alleged cases that occurred at Riau University and the formation of a Prevention Task Force and Handling Sexual Violence at the University of Riau. So that information regarding Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 can easily reach the academic community and be immediately responded to in an individual or institutional decision at the University of Riau.

The implementation stage will be easy to carry out in the diffusion of innovation if the community has decided to use innovation because innovation is considered to provide benefits and has positive value for adopters [23]. Positive values are also found in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 including:

1. The policy provides clear information on what is or is not included in sexual violence so that the target of the policy can avoid themselves from being

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either perpetrators of violence or victims of sexual violence

2. The policy provides comfort to the academic community that they are protected from sexual violence.

3. Policies are able to facilitate the needs of victims of violence through implementation standards for handling sexual violence

Stage of Confirmation

The results of the research which are in the confirmation stage on the diffusion of the Innovation Policy of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 30 of 2021 concerning the Prevention and Handling of Sexual Violence (PPKS) in Higher Education are 7 people or 7% of the total sample. At this stage a person looks for reinforcement for the decisions that have been taken to participate[24]. Confirmation is done by going through the process of

rethinking policy innovations to be continued or looking for other innovation alternatives. Strengthening will direct individuals to ensure their agreement or disapproval of each of the issues in Permendikbudristek Policy Number 30 of 2021.

Confirmation can also be done through group strengthening such as the results of research conducted by Hajaroh. The results of his research show that confirmation is in the form of strengthening the group[25]. Group strengthening within the University of Riau is still low. The low group reinforcement is shown only 7% of the sample is in the confirmation stage and is involved in group strengthening. Discussions on the issues contained in Permendikbudristek Number 30 of 2021 are still considered not feasible to be discussed together in a discussion group. This tendency can be caused by many things that need further research.

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